

Секція IV.

«ІННОВАЦІЙНІ МЕТОДИКИ ВИВЧЕННЯ ДИСЦИПЛІН ІНЖЕНЕРНО-ТЕХНІЧНОГО, ЕКОНОМІЧНОГО І ГУМАНІТАРНОГО ПРОФІЛЕЙ»

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USING INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN COUNTRY STUDIES AT KHAI

Today teachers use not only classical work formats, but also information technologies for teaching foreign students. The educational process of KhAI used specialized training services such as Google Class, Zoom, Hangouts, etc. Also, classroom work is supplemented by presentations with audio visualization tools, and digital platform Mentor is used for distance learning. The teaching process of foreign students includes the formation of the following basic skills: listening, reading, speaking, writing. All of these skills are formed not only during Ukrainian language learning, but also additional subjects learning which are in the curriculum of the preparatory department students. A more detailed analysis of this issue could be made on the example of the discipline "Country Studies" for foreign students of the preparatory department.

The aim of the discipline "Country Studies" is to ensure a close correlation between theoretical and practical training of foreign students. This discipline gives students practical experience following the curriculum of the program, makes the conditions for the formation of all types of educational competencies. As a result of studying the discipline "Country Studies", foreign students use linguistic material that they learned during language training and develop the communication skills necessary in everyday life. Thus, the main goal of the discipline is to prepare students for the effective use of Ukrainian as a foreign language and to consciously operate with various speech methods to ensure successful communication in different areas of life.

The experience in working at the preparatory department with foreign students shows the use of interactive technologies can significantly improve the quality of education and increase student activity, as well as stimulate their interest in studying the discipline. The curriculum in the discipline "Country Studies" is focused on the integrated implementation of the linguistic, practical, educational, general educational and developing goals of teaching the Ukrainian language as a foreign language. At the level of B1 language teaching, the practical goal is to improve the basic level of students' linguistic competence. The implementation of the educational goal involves

the formation of the need for students to improve their knowledge of Ukrainian as a foreign language and the formation of a steady interest in Ukraine country study. Developing and general educational goals involve the development of logical thinking in students, improving the ability to speak a foreign language, various types of memory, imagination, general speech, and general educational skills, etc.

Purposes of the discipline:

- to systematize and expand the basic knowledge of students about the culture and history of Ukraine;
- to contribute to the formation of students' skills of independent search and processing the lexical and information materials from various sources, including electronic databases;
- to explain the national psychological, behavioral, age and gender characteristics of Ukrainians;
- to make them read the modern scientific, methodological and reference literature on the problems of regional studies and intercultural communication;
- to form practical skills in working with texts on linguistic and regional studies topics;

For more than 5 years, teachers of KhAI have been using interactive technologies in Country Studies. Each topic of the course curriculum contains interactive lessons. The study of educational material is implemented by stages. The preparatory stage is the study of textual material (reading and understanding the text), at the second stage, additional information is provided through presentations, which are a source of additional lexical vocabulary. The next stage - watching video material contributes to the implementation of dialogical and monologue speech, and listening to audio materials improves listening skills. The next stage is the analysis and systematization of country studies information and tasks performing (using game teaching methods by working with an interactive board). The final stage is the demonstration of the work results (presentations on the chosen topic), work with materials and acquaintance with the cultural traditions of their native country is performed in the studied language (Ukrainian).

Thus, the discipline "Country Studies" form and develop a system of basic practical knowledge on the organization of work with materials of the country study, as well as their practical application. As an integral part of the educational process, the discipline "Country Studies" provides the consolidation of linguistic skills and their systematization. The analysis of the educational process makes it possible to confirm that working with interactive forms of educational material presentation is more productive than the classical educational approach.

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The article describes the experience of using interactive technology in teaching Ukrainian as a foreign language in the discipline "Country studies". The methodically correct use of modern multimedia tools in the classroom allows not only developing the certain speech skills more effectively, but also makes the learning process more interesting, stimulates the cognitive activity of students, and promotes better assimilation of the material studied.

Keywords: *Country studies, foreign language, foreign students*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО СТРАНОВЕДЕНИЮ В ХАИ

В статье описан опыт применения мультимедийной технологии в обучении украинскому языку как иностранному по дисциплине «Страноведение». Методически правильное использование современных мультимедийных средств на занятиях позволяет не только более эффективно развивать определенные речевые навыки, но также делает процесс обучения более интересным, стимулирует познавательную активность студентов, способствует лучшему усвоению изучаемого материала.

Ключевые слова: *Страноведение, иноземна мова, іноземні студенти.*